

2018 Usage Report for the IPCC DDC at CEDA

Document ownership and history		
Owner	CEDA	
Location	2018DDCUsage.docx	
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Version	1.0	
Date	2018-03-05	
Version history		
Date	Version	Comment
2018-03-05	0.1	Initial report for DDC managers.

Table of Contents

1.	Summary	1
2.	Evolution of User Sessions	2
3.	Access Patterns by Page on the DDC	3
4.	Geographical Distribution of Engagement with the DDC	5
5.	Browser Statistics	6
Appendix	A full breakdown by country of DDC user sessions	8

1. Summary

This report provides details of how the DDC web site, ipcc-data.org, was used in the 12 months from January 1st 2018 to December 31st 2018. The information presented here is generated using the Google Analytics service; providing a range of different statistics that cover both temporal and spatial trends. Only non-bounce sessions in which users have interacted with the website have been used in this analysis.

The annual DDC access statistics for 2018 show a marginal decrease in usage compared to 2017. The Home page remains the most commonly viewed page on the DDC.

Asia has become the most active region using DDC resources.

Of note is the increase in the usage of the website following the release of the IPCC 1.5 degree report [<https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/>] in October 2018.

2. Evolution of User Sessions

The number of DDC page views recorded in 2018 is marginally lower than the number of page views received in the previous year, from 181048 views in 2017 to 176307 views in 2018. Nevertheless the DDC continues to regularly receive over 2000 page views per week.

The usage of the DDC during 2018 is characterised by a spike of activity during a three day period from February 8th-11th (week 5) originating from users in China. There is also a step-change increase in page views after the release of the IPCC 1.5 degree report on October 8th (week 40 onwards).

Figure1: Time series of weekly DDC page views for non-bounce sessions. The time axis is shown in weeks from January 1st. Two time series are shown: red for the period from January 1st 2018 to December 31st 2018 and blue for the previous 12 months.

3. Access Patterns by Page on the DDC

The IPCC-DDC home page remains the most commonly viewed page on the DDC, receiving 13% of page views in 2018 (figure 3). Other popular pages are those that explain some of the basic science behind climate change such as: Understanding the observational record; Projected emissions and concentrations of carbon dioxide; An Introduction to Global Climate Models (GCMs). It is clear that users are interested in using the DDC to access GCM data and information about the IPCC 5th Assessment Report (AR5).

The access pattern of pages across the IPCC-DDC is very similar to the distribution recorded in the 2017 usage report.

Most users arriving at the DDC do so via the Home page. It is reassuring to know that the first DDC page users generally see is our home page because this is where we provide information about the purpose of the site and an overview of the content that we provide.

Most users visiting the guidance pages navigate there from another page on the DDC, this fits with the behaviour of a person who, having found some interesting data, decides to use our guidance documents to learn how to use it.

Again it is worth reiterating the importance of popular entry pages such as “What is a GCM?” and “CO2” as places where additional contextual information about the DDC can be placed. This is especially important to keep in mind when we move to a more modular site design in the future.

Distribution of page views across the DDC

Figure 3: Access distribution across the various pages of the IPCC-DDC that were visited during 2018.

Page on the DDC	URL	Number of Views	Percentage
Home	www.ipcc-data.org/index.html	23408	13.28
Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/index.html	12077	6.85
CO2	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/ddc_co2.html	9390	5.33
AR5 GCM data	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/AR5/index.html	7575	4.30
Simulations	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/index.html	7475	4.24
Scenario Process for AR5: RCPs	sedac.ipcc-data.org/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/RCPs.html	6443	3.65
AR4 GCM data	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/SRES_AR4/index.html	5938	3.37
Climate Model Output	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/index.html	5719	3.24
What is a GCM?	www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/gcm_guide.html	5067	2.87
AR4 Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/clim/ar4_global.html	4277	2.43
Guidance	www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/index.html	3950	2.24
Regional Scatter Plots	www.ipcc-data.org/syn/tar_scatter/index.html	3696	2.10
Environmental Data and Scenarios	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/ddc_envdata.html	3658	2.07
AR5 Reference Snapshot	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/AR5/Reference-Archive.html	3570	2.02
Climate Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/clim/index.html	3313	1.88

Table 1: The same information as in the pie chart in figure 3 but with the page URLs shown.

Access distribution across the DDC

Figure 4: The overall number of unique views per page (blue) and the number of entrances per page (red) during 2018. Users tend to arrive at pages where the number of entrances are about equal to the number of page views and navigate to pages where the number of entrances are much less than the number of page views.

4. Geographical Distribution of Engagement with the DDC

Distribution of Sessions by Continent

Figure 5

Figure 5: The geographical distribution of (non-bounce) DDC sessions by continent for 2018.

Geographical Distribution of Sessions by Country

Figure 6

Figure 6: The geographical distribution of (non-bounce) DDC user sessions by country for 2018.

Sessions initiated by users in Asia, Europe and North America account for 85% of DDC activity (figure 5) however approximately half of the DDC sessions are initiated by users in just eleven countries. Nevertheless the DDC plays an increasingly important role in many countries in spite of their relatively small number of page views.

Figure 6, which names the top 17 countries that make use of the DDC, is a useful way to showcase those countries that access the DDC most frequently. Users in the top 11 countries account for 51% of all sessions: USA 15%, China 8%, UK 6%, India 5%, Canada 4%, Germany 3%, France 2%, Australia 2%, Brazil 2%, Spain 2% and Italy 2%. “other” countries not listed here account for 41% of user sessions. 2018 has seen the proportion of sessions based in Asia rise to become the most active region of DDC usage. A full breakdown by country of the DDC user sessions is shown in appendix A.

5. Browser Statistics

The IPCC-DDC site is available and accessible to all the major internet browsers and operating systems. English is the most used language setting, accounting for 60% of sessions (figure 7). Chrome is the most popular browser, accounting for 68% of sessions and Windows is the most popular operating system, accounting for 77% of sessions (figure 8).

Distribution of Sessions by Browser Language

Figure 7

Figure 7: Language settings for DDC user sessions during 2018.

Sessions by Browser

Sessions by OS

Figure 8: Browser and technology characteristics of DDC user sessions with information about Browsers, Operating Systems that are used to access the DDC during 2018.

Appendix

A full breakdown, by country, of the (non-bounce) DDC user sessions during 2018.

Country	Sessions	Country	Sessions	Country	Sessions
United States	7159	Norway	194	Czechia	44
China	4048	Singapore	203	Bolivia	64
United Kingdom	3132	Chile	195	Côte d'Ivoire	48
India	2417	Greece	211	Serbia	47
Canada	1724	Russia	212	Israel	42
Germany	1552	Finland	170	Ghana	42
France	1070	New Zealand	157	Madagascar	39
Australia	950	Peru	171	Uganda	43
Brazil	881	Ireland	153	Benin	37
Spain	868	Nigeria	154	Honduras	41
Italy	918	Bangladesh	146	Cambodia	33
Netherlands	751	Argentina	163	Jordan	41
Japan	748	Morocco	186	Myanmar (Burma)	37
Iran	957	Kenya	146	Luxembourg	32
South Korea	580	Poland	124	Senegal	34
Sweden	573	Vietnam	129	Botswana	28
Mexico	410	Egypt	130	Lebanon	30
Switzerland	392	(not set)	102	Bulgaria	132
Indonesia	373	Saudi Arabia	102	Guatemala	25
Taiwan	428	Nepal	86	Croatia	22
Turkey	342	Sri Lanka	96	Kazakhstan	54
Portugal	340	Ecuador	88	Trinidad & Tobago	26
Thailand	335	Romania	78	Panama	23
Colombia	310	Hungary	69	Zambia	24
Denmark	271	United Arab Emirates	78	Slovenia	24
Pakistan	286	Algeria	63	Slovakia	22
South Africa	254	Tanzania	60	Brunei	19
Ethiopia	283	Costa Rica	73	Cyprus	22
Malaysia	289	Tunisia	159	Fiji	20
Philippines	229	Cameroon	52	Uzbekistan	24
Hong Kong	220	Iraq	71	Sudan	28
Belgium	216	Ukraine	50	Lithuania	19
Austria	195	Zimbabwe	53	Malta	23

Country	Sessions	Country	Sessions	Country	Sessions
Namibia	19	Mongolia	7	Somalia	2
Uruguay	18	Puerto Rico	7	Chad	4
Venezuela	17	Togo	7	Timor-Leste	4
Burkina Faso	15	Congo - Kinshasa	6	Turkmenistan	3
Latvia	15	Bosnia & Herzegovina	5	U.S. Virgin Islands	2
Malawi	13	Burundi	5	Kosovo	2
Mozambique	16	Belize	5	Andorra	1
Rwanda	14	Libya	5	Antigua & Barbuda	1
Dominican Republic	12	Papua New Guinea	10	Eritrea	1
Georgia	12	Réunion	5	Faroe Islands	1
Afghanistan	12	Sierra Leone	6	Gabon	1
Oman	13	Angola	4	Gambia	1
Paraguay	12	Bahrain	4	Guinea	1
El Salvador	14	Cape Verde	5	Jersey	1
Yemen	12	Djibouti	14	Kiribati	1
Estonia	16	Comoros	7	New Caledonia	1
Lesotho	10	Kuwait	5	Solomon Islands	1
Nicaragua	12	Macedonia (FYROM)	4	San Marino	1
Azerbaijan	10	Swaziland	4	South Sudan	1
Guyana	10	Armenia	8	St. Vincent & Grenadines	1
Iceland	12	Liberia	3	Vanuatu	2
Jamaica	13	Mauritania	4		
Mauritius	10	Suriname	3		
Niger	9	Barbados	2		
Albania	8	Bahamas	3		
Bhutan	9	Dominica	3		
Laos	10	Micronesia	2		
Mali	9	French Guiana	2		
Macau	8	Greenland	2		
Qatar	8	Haiti	2		
Syria	15	Kyrgyzstan	2		
Belarus	9	Montenegro	2		
Cuba	8	French Polynesia	2	Total	39402